

Time-independent perturbation theory: degeneracy lifted to the second order

Juan Álvarez Ruiz^{1,2,*} and Meijian Li^{1,†}

¹*Instituto Galego de Física de Altas Enerxías (IGFAE),*

Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, E-15782 Galicia, Spain

²*Heidelberg University, Grabengasse 1 69117 Heidelberg, Germany*

Although the fundamental principles of time-independent perturbation theory are well-established and widely applied, the specific treatment of degeneracy lifted to the second order remains largely unexplored. This work fills the gap by presenting a systematic derivation of time-independent perturbation theory that accounts for the added complexity introduced by non-trivial degeneracies. We provide a general procedure and corresponding formulae for calculating state and energy corrections to any order, with degeneracy lifted to the second order. To demonstrate the efficacy of the procedure, we apply these formulae to solve two toy model problems and a prototype problem of the dressed quark system.

I. THE TIME-INDEPENDENT PERTURBATION THEORY

The time-independent perturbation theory has been well-established in quantum mechanics and widely used to tackle various problems with Hamiltonian formalism. The basic idea is to start with a simple system for which the exact solution is known and add a term representing a perturbation to the Hamiltonian. Assuming that the perturbation is small, the eigenvalues and eigenstates of the perturbed system can be expressed as asymptotic series, in which “corrections” to those of the unperturbed simple system are expanded order by order. The complicated system can therefore be studied based on knowledge of the simpler one.

We make a systematic derivation of the time-independent perturbation theory. We start with the non-degenerate case, then the degenerate case with degeneracy lifted to the first order, and finally, the degenerate case with degeneracy lifted to the second order. Reviews of the time-independent perturbation theory can be found in various textbooks of quantum mechanics, e.g., Refs. [1, 2] provide methods for the first two cases, Ref. [3] discussed the elementary theory for the degenerate cases, and Ref. [4] provides a derivation for the last case but only in a special situation (degeneracy completely unbroken to first order) and in the lowest orders.

A. Perturbation of a non-degenerate system

Suppose that the problem Hamiltonian can be written as a summation of an unperturbed Hamiltonian H_0 and a perturbation δH . The exact solution of the Time-Independent Schrödinger Equation (TISE) with H_0 is known,

$$H_0 |\psi_n^{(0)}\rangle = E_n^{(0)} |\psi_n^{(0)}\rangle, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad (1)$$

where $|\psi_n^{(0)}\rangle$ the n -th normalized eigenstate with eigenvalue $E_n^{(0)}$, with N the dimension of the problem space. Here, we consider a non-degenerate system, which means that

$$E_n^{(0)} \neq E_m^{(0)}, \text{ for } n \neq m. \quad (2)$$

Now we want to calculate the solution to the problem given by the perturbed Hamiltonian $H = H_0 + \lambda\delta H$ with λ a real variable. The perturbed TISE for the n -th eigenstate becomes

$$(H_0 + \lambda\delta H) |\psi_n\rangle = E_n |\psi_n\rangle. \quad (3)$$

* juan.alvarez.ruiz@stud.uni-heidelberg.de

† meijian.li@usc.es

At $\lambda = 0$, we recover the unperturbed problem as in Eq. (1). We can then expect the solution to the problem be dependent on λ with the limit case of recovering the original solution for $\lambda \rightarrow 0$. We expand the eigenvalues and eigenstates as a power series of λ :

$$E_n = E_n^{(0)} + E_n^{(1)}\lambda + E_n^{(2)}\lambda^2 + \mathcal{O}(\lambda^3) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} E_n^{(i)}\lambda^i, \quad (4a)$$

$$|\psi_n\rangle = |\psi_n^{(0)}\rangle + |\psi_n^{(1)}\rangle\lambda + |\psi_n^{(2)}\rangle\lambda^2 + \mathcal{O}(\lambda^3) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} |\psi_n^{(i)}\rangle\lambda^i. \quad (4b)$$

Here and throughout the paper, we use the upper index with parenthesis “(i)” to denote the coefficient at i -th order of λ . We impose a condition that all the state corrections contain no vector along the unperturbed state, without loss of generality [4],

$$\langle\psi_n^{(0)}|\psi_n^{(i)}\rangle = \delta_{i,0}, \quad i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad (5)$$

and it follows from Eq. (4b) that $\langle\psi_n^{(0)}|\psi_n\rangle = 1$.

Putting Eqs. (4b) and (4a) back to Eq. (3), we get

$$(H_0 + \lambda\delta H) \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} |\psi_n^{(i)}\rangle\lambda^i = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} E_n^{(j)}\lambda^j \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} |\psi_n^{(k)}\rangle\lambda^k. \quad (6)$$

By reordering the terms, we align the left- and the right-hand-sides in orders of λ ,

$$H_0 |\psi_n^{(0)}\rangle + \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} [H_0 |\psi_n^{(i)}\rangle + \delta H |\psi_n^{(i-1)}\rangle] \lambda^i = E_n^{(0)} |\psi_n^{(0)}\rangle + \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \left[\sum_{j=0}^i E_n^{(j)} |\psi_n^{(i-j)}\rangle \right] \lambda^i. \quad (7)$$

The equation holds only if it is the case at each order of λ . Therefore, we have,

$$H_0 |\psi_n^{(0)}\rangle = E_n^{(0)} |\psi_n^{(0)}\rangle, \quad (8)$$

at the 0-th order of λ , recovering the original TISE, and

$$H_0 |\psi_n^{(i)}\rangle + \delta H |\psi_n^{(i-1)}\rangle - \sum_{j=0}^i E_n^{(j)} |\psi_n^{(i-j)}\rangle = 0, \quad (9)$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots$, from which one can solve for the perturbed wavefunction and energy. In the following, we will work out the calculation up to the second order.

1. The first order correction

To obtain first order correction to the eigenvalue $E_n^{(1)}$, we project Eq. (9) with index $i = 1$ on the eigenstate $\langle\psi_n^{(0)}|$,

$$\langle\psi_n^{(0)}|H_0|\psi_n^{(1)}\rangle + \langle\psi_n^{(0)}|\delta H|\psi_n^{(0)}\rangle - E_n^{(0)} \langle\psi_n^{(0)}|\psi_n^{(1)}\rangle - E_n^{(1)} \langle\psi_n^{(0)}|\psi_n^{(0)}\rangle = 0. \quad (10)$$

The first and third terms cancel out and we end up with,

$$E_n^{(1)} = \langle\psi_n^{(0)}|\delta H|\psi_n^{(0)}\rangle. \quad (11)$$

$$H_0 = \begin{pmatrix} E_1^{(0)} & & & \\ & E_2^{(0)} & & \\ & & \ddots & \\ & & & E_n^{(0)} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \delta H = \begin{pmatrix} E_1^{(1)} & & & \\ & E_2^{(1)} & & \\ & & \ddots & \\ & & & E_n^{(1)} \end{pmatrix}$$

FIG. 1. For a non-degenerate system, in the basis of the unperturbed Hamiltonian H_0 eigenstates, the diagonal matrix elements of the perturbation δH gives the 1st order energy correction.

It means that the diagonal matrix elements of δH gives the 1st order energy correction, as illustrated in Fig. 1. For simplicity, let us define $\delta H_{m,n} \equiv \langle \psi_m^{(0)} | \delta H | \psi_n^{(0)} \rangle$, such that $E_n^{(1)} = \delta H_{n,n}$. To obtain the first order correction to the eigenstate, we write the first order correction in terms of the unperturbed basis states,

$$|\psi_n^{(1)}\rangle = \sum_m |\psi_m^{(0)}\rangle \langle \psi_m^{(0)} | \psi_n^{(1)} \rangle = \sum_{m \neq n} c_m^{(n)(1)} |\psi_m^{(0)}\rangle, \quad (12)$$

in which we have applied the condition in Eq. (5). To find the coefficients $c_m^{(n)(1)}$, we project Eq. (9) with index $i = 1$ on the eigenstate $\langle \psi_j^{(0)} |$ where $j \neq n$,

$$\langle \psi_j^{(0)} | H_0 | \psi_n^{(1)} \rangle + \langle \psi_j^{(0)} | \delta H | \psi_n^{(0)} \rangle - E_n^{(0)} \langle \psi_j^{(0)} | \psi_n^{(1)} \rangle - E_n^{(1)} \langle \psi_j^{(0)} | \psi_n^{(0)} \rangle = 0. \quad (13)$$

The last term vanishes by orthogonality, and we are left with

$$c_j^{(n)(1)} (E_j^{(0)} - E_n^{(0)}) = - \langle \psi_j^{(0)} | \delta H | \psi_n^{(0)} \rangle. \quad (14)$$

To proceed, we restrict the discussion for non-degenerate systems by requiring $E_j^{(0)} \neq E_n^{(0)}$ when $j \neq n$, and we will treat degenerate systems in the next section. It follows that

$$c_j^{(n)(1)} = - \frac{\delta H_{j,n}}{E_j^{(0)} - E_n^{(0)}}. \quad (15)$$

2. Higher order correction

We can generalize the aforementioned procedure for higher order corrections, for which we obtain a recursive relation of the corrections. We first find the corrections to the energy by projecting Eq. (9) to $|\psi_n^{(0)}\rangle$,

$$\langle \psi_n^{(0)} | H_0 | \psi_n^{(i)} \rangle + \langle \psi_n^{(0)} | \delta H | \psi_n^{(i-1)} \rangle - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} E_n^{(j)} \langle \psi_n^{(0)} | \psi_n^{(i-j)} \rangle - E_n^{(0)} \langle \psi_n^{(0)} | \psi_n^{(i)} \rangle = E_n^{(i)} \langle \psi_n^{(0)} | \psi_n^{(0)} \rangle, \quad (16)$$

in which we write out the two terms at $j = 0$ and $j = i$ in the original summation. The first and fourth terms cancel out by seeing that $|\psi_n^{(0)}\rangle$ is the eigenstate of H_0 with eigenvalue $E_n^{(0)}$. The third term vanishes by orthogonality. We therefore have

$$\boxed{E_n^{(i)} = \langle \psi_n^{(0)} | \delta H | \psi_n^{(i-1)} \rangle, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots} \quad (17)$$

This means that the i -th order energy correction can be determined by knowing the $(i - 1)$ -th order state correction. In particular, the second order correction is, with knowing $|\psi_n^{(1)}\rangle$ from Eq. (15),

$$E_n^{(2)} = \sum_{m \neq n} \frac{|\delta H_{m,n}|^2}{E_n^{(0)} - E_m^{(0)}}. \quad (18)$$

Similar to the treatment with the first order state correction, we expand the i -th order eigenstates in terms of the unperturbed basis states,

$$|\psi_n^{(i)}\rangle = \sum_m c_m^{(n)(i)} |\psi_m^{(0)}\rangle. \quad (19)$$

The orthonormal condition of the unperturbed states gives $c_m^{(n)(0)} = \delta_{m,n}$ and the condition of the state correction given by Eq. (5) can be written as $c_n^{(n)(i)} = 0$ when $i \geq 1$.

To find the coefficients, we project Eq. (9) on the eigenstate $\langle \psi_k^{(0)} |$ with $k \neq n$,

$$c_k^{(n)(i)} (E_k^{(0)} - E_n^{(0)}) + \sum_m c_m^{(n)(i-1)} \langle \psi_k^{(0)} | \delta H | \psi_m^{(0)} \rangle - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} E_n^{(j)} c_k^{(n)(i-j)} = 0. \quad (20)$$

Note that in the last summation, the $j = i$ term vanishes due to state orthogonality. The above equation provides a recursive relation for the coefficient $c_k^{(n)(i)}$ at different order i . For a non-degenerate system, where $E_k^{(0)} \neq E_n^{(0)}$ for $k \neq n$, one can solve for $c_k^{(n)(i)}$ as

$$c_k^{(n)(i)} = \frac{1}{E_k^{(0)} - E_n^{(0)}} \left[- \sum_m c_m^{(n)(i-1)} \delta H_{k,m} + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} E_n^{(j)} c_k^{(n)(i-j)} \right]. \quad (21)$$

We can thereby summarize a general procedure for the perturbative theory of a non-degenerate system: On a basis space generated by the unperturbed eigenstates of H_0 , calculate the perturbation correction according to Eqs. (17) and (21) order by order.

B. Perturbation of a degenerate system, degeneracy lifted to the first order

Now we consider perturbation theory in a degenerate case, where for the initial Hamiltonian there are more than one eigenstates having the same eigenvalue. The procedure for non-degenerate systems as described in Sec. IA no longer fully applies, as Eqs. (18) and (21) can become singular with $E_k^0 - E_n^0 = 0$ ($k \neq n$) in the denominator.

Without loss of generality, suppose there is a g -fold degeneracy in the unperturbed Hamiltonian, i.e., there are g eigenstates of H_0 with the same eigenvalue $E_D^{(0)}$.¹ We denote these states by $\{|D; m^{(0)}\rangle\}$ with $m = 1, 2, \dots, g$, and their spanned subspace by D . The Hilbert space can be written as $\mathcal{H} = D \oplus V_\perp$, in which V_\perp is the non-degenerate subspace orthogonal to D and one can calculate its perturbation by using the non-degenerate perturbation procedure as explained in Sec. IA.

Note that due to the degeneracy, any linear combination of $\{|D; m^{(0)}\rangle\}$ is also an eigenstate of H_0 with eigenvalue $E_D^{(0)}$. In order to compute the state and energy correction in powers of λ , as in Eq. (4b) and Eq. (4a), we need to use the correct unperturbed state that the corresponding perturbed state would approach in the limit $\lambda \rightarrow 0$. Let us denote the states of the subspace D after perturbation as $\{|D; n\rangle\}$ with $n = 1, 2, \dots, g$,

¹ In cases with multiple degenerate subspaces, say D_1, D_2, \dots , each having a different eigenvalue $E_{D_1}^{(0)}, E_{D_2}^{(0)}, \dots$, one can apply the procedure described in this section to each subspace.

FIG. 2. For a system with degeneracy, diagonalizing the perturbation δH in the degenerate subspace D leads to finding the “good basis” and the 1st order energy correction. The perturbation Hamiltonian diagonalized in D is denoted as $\delta \tilde{H}$.

which in general do not belong to D but in the limit of $\lambda \rightarrow 0$ become $\{|D; n^{(0)}\rangle\}$. The set $\{|D; n^{(0)}\rangle\}$ is a basis of D , which however are not necessarily the same with $\{|D; m^{(0)}\rangle\}$. As such, we have

$$|D; n\rangle = |D; n^{(0)}\rangle + |D; n^{(1)}\rangle \lambda + |D; n^{(2)}\rangle \lambda^2 + \mathcal{O}(\lambda^3), \quad (22)$$

$$E_{D;n} = E_D^{(0)} + E_{D;n}^{(1)} \lambda + E_{D;n}^{(2)} \lambda^2 + \mathcal{O}(\lambda^3). \quad (23)$$

As before, we use the convention that $\{|D; n^{(i)}\rangle\}$ is orthonormal.

1. First order equation

Similar to the procedure in the non-degenerate case, we extract the information of the perturbation by projecting the eigenvalue equation to different basis states. Here, we project the first order TISE, i.e., Eq. (9) with index $i = 1$, on $\langle D; l^{(0)}|$, an arbitrary state in the set $\{|D; n^{(0)}\rangle\}$ that we are looking for,

$$\langle D; l^{(0)}|H_0|D; n^{(1)}\rangle + \langle D; l^{(0)}|\delta H|D; n^{(0)}\rangle - E_D^{(0)} \langle D; l^{(0)}|D; n^{(1)}\rangle - E_{D;n}^{(1)} \langle D; l^{(0)}|D; n^{(0)}\rangle = 0. \quad (24)$$

The first and third terms cancel out and we end up with,

$$E_{D;n}^{(1)} \delta_{n,l} = \langle D; l^{(0)}|\delta H|D; n^{(0)}\rangle. \quad (25)$$

This means that the basis $\{|D; n^{(0)}\rangle\}$ diagonalizes δH in D , and $E_{D;n}^{(1)}$ s are the eigenvalues, as illustrated in Fig. 2. For simplicity, let us define $\delta H_{D;n,D;n} \equiv \langle D; n^{(0)}|\delta H|D; n^{(0)}\rangle$, such that $E_{D;n}^{(1)} = \delta H_{D;n,D;n}$.

To continue, we project the same first order TISE, onto a state in the V_\perp subspace, $\langle \psi_p^{(0)} |$,

$$\langle \psi_p^{(0)} | H_0 | D; n^{(1)} \rangle + \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | \delta H | D; n^{(0)} \rangle - E_D^{(0)} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D; n^{(1)} \rangle - E_{D;n}^{(1)} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D; n^{(0)} \rangle = 0. \quad (26)$$

The last term vanishes due to orthogonality, and we are left with

$$\langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D; n^{(1)} \rangle = -\frac{\delta H_{p,D;n}}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}}, \quad (27)$$

in which we have defined $\delta H_{p,D;n} \equiv \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | \delta H | D; n^{(0)} \rangle$ for convenience. Note that we only get the part of the first order state in the V_\perp subspace, and that in D is still missing,

$$|D; n^{(1)}\rangle = \sum_{p \notin D} |\psi_p^{(0)}\rangle \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D; n^{(1)} \rangle + \sum_{l \in D, l \neq n} |D; l^{(0)}\rangle \langle D; l^{(0)} | D; n^{(1)} \rangle. \quad (28)$$

2. Second order equation

We project the second order TISE, i.e., Eq. (9) with index $i = 2$, onto $\langle D; l^{(0)} |$,

$$\langle D; l^{(0)} | (H_0 - E_D^{(0)}) | D; n^{(2)} \rangle - \langle D; l^{(0)} | (E_{D;n}^{(1)} - \delta H) | D; n^{(1)} \rangle - E_{D;n}^{(2)} \langle D; l^{(0)} | D; n^{(0)} \rangle = 0. \quad (29)$$

The first term vanishes immediately. We plug in Eq. (28), and after some simplification, arrive at

$$(E_{D;n}^{(1)} - E_{D;l}^{(1)}) \langle D; l^{(0)} | D; n^{(1)} \rangle - \sum_{p \notin D} \delta H_{D;l,p} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D; n^{(1)} \rangle + E_{D;n}^{(2)} \delta_{l,n} = 0. \quad (30)$$

We already know the second term from Eq. (27). We take $l \neq n$ to extract the remaining information in $|D; n^{(1)}\rangle$. Here, we assume that the degeneracy is completely resolved so that $E_{D;n}^{(1)} \neq E_{D;l}^{(1)}$ when $l \neq n$. Therefore,

$$\langle D; l^{(0)} | D; n^{(1)} \rangle = \sum_{p \notin D} -\frac{\delta H_{D;l,p} \delta H_{p,D;n}}{(E_{D;n}^{(1)} - E_{D;l}^{(1)})(E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)})}. \quad (31)$$

We obtain the first order state correction with Eqs. (28), (27), and (31). An alternative derivation using projectors of the above method is in Appendix A. We take $l = n$ in Eq. (30) and obtain the second order energy correction as

$$E_{D;n}^{(2)} = \sum_{p \notin D} -\frac{|\delta H_{p,D;n}|^2}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}}. \quad (32)$$

To complete the calculation at the second order equation, let us project the second order TISE onto a state in the V_\perp subspace, $\langle \psi_p^{(0)} |$,

$$\langle \psi_p^{(0)} | (H_0 - E_D^{(0)}) | D; n^{(2)} \rangle - \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | (E_{D;n}^{(1)} - \delta H) | D; n^{(1)} \rangle - E_{D;n}^{(2)} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D; n^{(0)} \rangle = 0. \quad (33)$$

The last term vanishes due to state orthogonality, and the first order corrections are already known. We therefore get the second order state correction in the V_\perp subspace,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D; n^{(2)} \rangle = & \frac{1}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} \left[E_{D;n}^{(1)} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D; n^{(1)} \rangle - \sum_{q \notin D} \delta H_{p,q} \langle \psi_q^{(0)} | D; n^{(1)} \rangle \right. \\ & \left. - \sum_{l \in D, l \neq n} \delta H_{p,D;l} \langle D; l^{(0)} | D; n^{(1)} \rangle \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

3. Higher order corrections

Let us generalize the aforementioned procedure for higher order corrections. Note that for states in the V_{\perp} subspace, the results shown in Sec. IA apply directly, and here we make the derivation for the states in the D subspace. The i -th order eigenstates in terms of the unperturbed basis states can be written as,

$$|D; n^{(i)}\rangle = (P_{V_{\perp}} + P_D) |D; n^{(i)}\rangle = \sum_{p \notin D} |\psi_p^{(0)}\rangle c_p^{(D;n)(i)} + \sum_{l \in D} |D; l^{(0)}\rangle c_{D;l}^{(D;n)(i)}, \quad (35)$$

in which $c_p^{(D;n)(i)} \equiv \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D; n^{(i)} \rangle$ and $c_{D;l}^{(D;n)(i)} \equiv \langle D; l^{(0)} | D; n^{(i)} \rangle$. The orthonormal condition of the unperturbed states gives $c_{D;l}^{(D;n)(0)} = \delta_{l,n}$ and the condition of the state correction given by Eq. (5) can be written as $c_{D;l}^{(D;n)(i)} = 0$ when $i \geq 1$.

From the i -th order TISE, we can get $E_{D;n}^{(i)}$, $c_p^{(D;n)(i)}$ s and $c_{D;l}^{(D;n)(i-1)}$ s ($i \geq 2$ for the last one) in terms of lower order results. We have already shown this with the first and second order equations. Let us proceed with the i -th order equation, as of Eq. (9),

$$H_0 |D; n^{(i)}\rangle + \delta H |D; n^{(i-1)}\rangle - \sum_{j=0}^i E_{D;n}^{(j)} |D; n^{(i-j)}\rangle = 0, \quad (36)$$

in the following.

- Projection onto V_{\perp}

By projecting Eq. (36) onto a state in the V_{\perp} subspace, $\langle \psi_p^{(0)} |$, we get

$$(E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}) \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D; n^{(i)} \rangle + \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | \delta H | D; n^{(i-1)} \rangle - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} E_{D;n}^{(j)} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D; n^{(i-j)} \rangle = 0. \quad (37)$$

Expanding the state correction with Eq. (35), we get

$$c_p^{(D;n)(i)} = -\frac{1}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} \left[\sum_{q \notin D} \delta H_{p,q} c_q^{(D;n)(i-1)} + \sum_{l \in D} \delta H_{p,D;l} c_{D;l}^{(D;n)(i-1)} - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} E_{D;n}^{(j)} c_p^{(D;n)(i-j)} \right]. \quad (38)$$

All terms on the right-hand side are already known from lower order equations. This formula is essentially the same with Eq. (21), implying that the perturbation correction a state receives from the non-degenerate subspace is the same as that in the non-degenerate case.

- Projection onto D

By projecting Eq. (36) onto a state in the D subspace, $\langle D; l^{(0)} |$, we get

$$\langle D; l^{(0)} | \delta H | D; n^{(i-1)} \rangle - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} E_{D;n}^{(j)} \langle D; l^{(0)} | D; n^{(i-j)} \rangle - E_{D;n}^{(i)} \langle D; l^{(0)} | D; n^{(0)} \rangle = 0. \quad (39)$$

In the case of $l = n$, we have

$$E_{D;n}^{(i)} = \langle D; n^{(0)} | \delta H | D; n^{(i-1)} \rangle. \quad (40)$$

In the case of $l \neq n$, we have

$$c_{D;l}^{(D;n)(i-1)} = \frac{1}{E_{D;l}^{(1)} - E_{D;n}^{(1)}} \left[\sum_{j=2}^{i-1} E_{D;n}^{(j)} c_{D;l}^{(D;n)(i-j)} - \sum_{p \notin D} \delta H_{D;l,p} c_p^{(D;n)(i-1)} \right]. \quad (41)$$

In comparison to the non-degenerate formula Eq. (21), we see the difference is that here the summation over δH elements excludes all contributions from the degenerate subspace D , and the energy difference in the denominator is at the first instead of the zeroth order as the latter already cancels out by degeneracy.

We can now summarize a general procedure for the perturbative theory of a degenerate system whose degeneracy is resolved at first order:

1. On a basis space generated by the unperturbed eigenstates of H_0 , identify the degenerate subspace D . Diagonalize δH in the degenerate subspace, and take the δH eigenstates as the new unperturbed states in the degenerate subspace; the corresponding eigenvalues give the first order state correction.
2. Calculate the perturbation correction to the states whose unperturbed states are in the degenerate subspace according to Eqs. (38), (40), and (41).
3. Calculate the perturbation correction to the states whose unperturbed states are in the non-degenerate subspace according to Eqs. (17) and (21).

C. Perturbation of a degenerate system, degeneracy lifted to the second order

When the degeneracy is not removed completely in first order, the method described in Sec. IB fails, specifically eq. (31) becomes singular. In other words, we cannot determine the correct zeroth-order basis states with the information up to the first order perturbation. In this section, we consider the scenario where the degeneracy is not or only partly resolved at first order, and completely resolved at second order.

We consider a system with a g -fold degeneracy on a subspace D . We carry on the setup that the full Hilbert space of the problem can be written as $\mathcal{H} = D \oplus \mathbb{V}_\perp$. The subspace D is spanned by the unperturbed eigenstates $\{|D; n^{(0)}\rangle\}$ ($n = 1, 2, \dots, g$) (with unperturbed eigenvalue $E_D^{(0)}$) that already diagonalize the perturbation δH in D . Their first order corrections, as can be obtained by Eq. (25), are $\{E_{D_1}^{(1)}, E_{D_2}^{(1)}, \dots, E_{D_B}^{(1)}\}$ where $B < g$; note that in the scenario of $B = g$ the degeneracy is completely broken at first order and the problem is solved according to the procedure in Sec. IB. We now express D as a direct sum of the subspaces with different first order correction, $D = \bigoplus_{I=1}^B D_I$, where D_I is the subspace spanned by the unperturbed eigenstates that have the same first order energy correction $E_{D_I}^{(1)}$. The dimensions of D_I is N_I such that $\sum_{I=1}^B N_I = g$. For convenience, let us denote the unperturbed basis states $\{|D; n^{(0)}\rangle\}$ that are in the D_I subspace with the subscript I as $\{|D_I; n_I^{(0)}\rangle\}$ ($n_I = 1, 2, \dots, N_I$). For a subspace D_I with $N_I > 1$, any linear combination of $\{|D; n^{(0)}\rangle\}$ is still a H_0 eigenstate with eigenvalue $E_D^{(0)}$, and our goal here is to find the ‘‘good basis’’ that the corresponding perturbed state would approach in the limit $\lambda \rightarrow 0$.

Let us denote the ‘‘good basis’’ by $\{|D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)}\rangle\}$ ($\alpha_I = 1, 2, \dots, N_I$), for which we use Greek letters as the state index to distinguish those of the original basis. We can write the α_I -th state of the D_I subspace as linear a combination of the original basis states,

$$|D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)}\rangle = \sum_{n_I=1}^{N_I} v_{n_I}^{\alpha_I} |D_I; n_I^{(0)}\rangle. \quad (42)$$

Here, $v_{n_I}^{\alpha_I} \equiv \langle D_I; n_I^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)} \rangle$. Note that δH remains diagonal in D with the ‘‘good basis’’. With the ‘‘good basis’’, we can expand the corresponding perturbed state and energy in powers of λ ,

$$|D_I; \alpha_I\rangle = |D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)}\rangle + |D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle \lambda + |D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)}\rangle \lambda^2 + \mathcal{O}(\lambda^3), \quad (43)$$

$$E_{D_I; \alpha_I} = E_D^{(0)} + E_{D_I}^{(1)} \lambda + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \lambda^2 + \mathcal{O}(\lambda^3). \quad (44)$$

FIG. 3. For a system with degeneracy lifted to the second order, diagonalizing the perturbation δH in the $E^{(0)}$ -degenerate subspace D does not completely break the degeneracy (c.f. Fig. 2), and we have $D = D_1 \oplus D_2 \oplus \dots \oplus D_{N_I}$, where D_I s are $E^{(1)}$ -degenerate subspaces. The “good basis” diagonalizes $\Delta_{D_I}^{(2)}$ as defined in Eq. (57). The red circles denote the matrix elements involved in calculating $\Delta_{D_I}^{(2)}|_{m_1, n_1}$ as an example.

As before, we apply the orthogonality condition on $\{|D_I; \alpha_I^{(i)}\rangle\}$ as defined in Eq. (5). The eigenvalue equation, as of Eq. (9), for $|D_I; \alpha_I^{(i)}\rangle$, becomes

$$\mathcal{O}(1) : (H_0 - E_D^{(0)}) |D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)}\rangle = 0, \quad (45)$$

$$\mathcal{O}(\lambda) : (H_0 - E_D^{(0)}) |D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle = (E_{D_I}^{(1)} - \delta H) |D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)}\rangle, \quad (46)$$

$$\mathcal{O}(\lambda^2) : (H_0 - E_D^{(0)}) |D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)}\rangle = (E_{D_I}^{(1)} - \delta H) |D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)}\rangle, \quad (47)$$

$$\mathcal{O}(\lambda^3) : (H_0 - E_D^{(0)}) |D_I; \alpha_I^{(3)}\rangle = (E_{D_I}^{(1)} - \delta H) |D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)}\rangle + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(3)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)}\rangle, \quad (48)$$

⋮

Equation (45) is satisfied by definition of the basis state.

1. First order equation

From the first order equation, we can get the first order energy correction $E_{D_I}^{(1)} = \delta H_{D_I; \alpha_I, D_I; \alpha_I}$ as in Eq. (25), and the part of the first order state correction in the \mathbb{V}_\perp subspace, which, in analogy to Eq. (27), is

$$\langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle = -\frac{\delta H_{p, D_I; \alpha_I}}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} = -\frac{\sum_{n_I=1}^{N_I} v_{n_I}^{\alpha_I} \delta H_{p, D_I; n_I}}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}}. \quad (49)$$

We have defined $\delta H_{p, D_I; \alpha_I} \equiv \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | \delta H | D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)} \rangle$ and similarly, $\delta H_{p, D_I; n_I} \equiv \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | \delta H | D_I; n_I^{(0)} \rangle$ for convenience, and recall that $|D_I; n_I^{(0)}\rangle$ is just $|D; n^{(0)}\rangle$ in Eq. (27) with the subspace index I written out.

2. Second order equation

Continuing with the second order equation, different from the treatment in Sec. **IB**, here we need to take into account the remaining degeneracy after applying the first order perturbation. In consequence, in place of Eq. 28, we project $|D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle$ onto three subspaces, \mathbb{V}_\perp , $D - D_I$, and D_I ,

$$\begin{aligned} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle &= (\mathbb{P}_{\mathbb{V}_\perp} + \mathbb{P}_{D-D_I} + \mathbb{P}_{D_I}) |D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle \\ &= \sum_{p \neq D} |\psi_p^{(0)}\rangle \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle + \sum_{J \neq I} \sum_{n_J=1}^{N_J} |D_J; n_J^{(0)}\rangle \langle D_J; n_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle \\ &\quad + \sum_{n_I=1}^{N_I} |D_I; n_I^{(0)}\rangle \langle D_I; n_I^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle . \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

In the second equation, we write out the projection in the original basis, which is also true with the ‘‘good basis’’. The projection onto $D - D_I$ gives us part of the first order state correction. Written explicitly, projecting Eq. (47) onto $\langle D_J; n_J^{(0)} |$ with $J \neq I$, we get

$$\langle D_J; n_J^{(0)} | (H_0 - E_D^{(0)}) | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)}\rangle = \langle D_J; n_J^{(0)} | (E_{D_I}^{(1)} - \delta H) | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \langle D_J; n_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)}\rangle . \quad (51)$$

The first term vanishes by noting $H_0 \rightarrow E_D^{(0)}$, and the last term vanishes due to orthogonality. In the remaining term, we apply Eq. (50), and obtain

$$E_{D_I}^{(1)} \langle D_J; n_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle = \sum_{p \neq D} \delta H_{D_J; n_J, p} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle + \delta H_{D_J; n_J, D_J; n_J} \langle D_J; n_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle . \quad (52)$$

Putting together with Eq. (49), we have

$$\langle D_J; n_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle = \sum_{p \neq D} - \frac{\delta H_{D_J; n_J, p} \delta H_{p, D_I; \alpha_I}}{(E_{D_I}^{(1)} - E_{D_I}^{(1)}) (E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)})} . \quad (53)$$

This result is similar to Eq. (31), and recovers the latter when $N_I = 1$.

Next, we project Eq. (47) onto D_I ,

$$\langle D_I; n_I^{(0)} | (H_0 - E_D^{(0)}) | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)}\rangle = \langle D_I; n_I^{(0)} | (E_{D_I}^{(1)} - \delta H) | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \langle D_I; n_I^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)}\rangle . \quad (54)$$

Again, the first term vanishes, and we recognize $v_{n_I}^{\alpha_I}$ in the last term. We apply Eq. (50), and obtain

$$\sum_{p \neq D} \delta H_{D_I; n_I, p} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle - E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} v_{n_I}^{\alpha_I} = 0 . \quad (55)$$

We have applied in the above equation that δH is diagonal in D and $E_{D_I}^{(1)} = \delta H_{D_I; n_I, D_I; n_I}$. Putting together with Eq. (49), we have

$$- \sum_{p \neq D} \delta H_{D_I; n_I, p} \frac{\sum_{m_I=1}^{N_I} v_{m_I}^{\alpha_I} \delta H_{p, D_I; m_I}}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} - E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} v_{n_I}^{\alpha_I} = 0 . \quad (56)$$

Let us rewrite the above equation by defining the operator $\Delta_{D_I}^{(2)}$, with matrix elements

$$\Delta_{D_I}^{(2)} |n_I, m_I\rangle = \langle D_I; n_I^{(0)} | \Delta_{D_I}^{(2)} |D_I; m_I^{(0)}\rangle \equiv - \sum_{p \neq D} \frac{\delta H_{D_I; n_I, p} \delta H_{p, D_I; m_I}}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} . \quad (57)$$

Physically, this is the energy fluctuation of an initial state in D_I going through any intermediate states in \mathbb{V}_\perp and back to D_I . Equation (56) can be written as

$$\boxed{\sum_{m_I=1}^{N_I} [\Delta_{D_I}^{(2)}|n_I, m_I\rangle - E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \delta_{n_I, m_I}] v_{m_I}^{\alpha_I} = 0,} \quad (58)$$

which is clearly an eigenvalue equation of vectors $\mathbf{v}^{\alpha_I} \equiv \{v_1^{\alpha_I}, v_2^{\alpha_I}, \dots, v_{n_I}^{\alpha_I}\}$, with $\alpha_I = 1, 2, \dots, N_I$. We therefore find the ‘‘good basis’’ by solving \mathbf{v}^{α_I} as the eigenvectors of $\Delta_{D_I}^{(2)}$, and in the meantime, we obtain the second order energy correction $E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)}$ as the eigenvalues. We illustrate the relation of $\Delta_{D_I}^{(2)}$ and the δH matrix in Fig. 3. Lastly, let us project Eq. (47) onto \mathbb{V}_\perp ,

$$\langle \psi_p^{(0)} | (H_0 - E_D^{(0)}) | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle = \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | (E_{D_I}^{(1)} - \delta H) | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)} \rangle. \quad (59)$$

The last term vanishes by orthogonality. Decomposing the first order state by Eq. (50), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle = & \frac{1}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} \left\{ E_{D_I}^{(1)} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle - \sum_{q \notin D} \delta H_{p,q} \langle \psi_q^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle \right. \\ & \left. - \sum_{J \neq I} \sum_{n_J=1}^{N_J} \delta H_{p, D_J; n_J} \langle D_J; n_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle - \sum_{n_I=1}^{N_I} \delta H_{p, D_I; n_I} \langle D_I; n_I^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

The first three terms on the right-hand side of the equation are known by Eqs. (49) and (53). What we have is a relation between two unknowns, the second order and the first order states. So far, the last piece of the first order state correction is still missing, i.e., the last term in Eq. (50). We have, however, exhausted the information of the eigenvalue equations up to $O(\lambda^2)$. We need to proceed with the third order equation.

3. Third order equation

We first project Eq. (48) onto D_I , and now that we have found the ‘‘good basis’’, we shall use $\langle D_I; \beta_I^{(0)} |$. This gives us the

$$\begin{aligned} \langle D_I; \beta_I^{(0)} | (H_0 - E_D^{(0)}) | D_I; \alpha_I^{(3)} \rangle = & \langle D_I; \beta_I^{(0)} | (E_{D_I}^{(1)} - \delta H) | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle \\ & + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \langle D_I; \beta_I^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(3)} \langle D_I; \beta_I^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)} \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

The terms on the left-hand side cancel out. In the case $\beta_I = \alpha_I$, we get, by applying the orthogonality condition of $|D_I; \alpha_I^{(i)}\rangle$ with respect to $|D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)}\rangle$ as defined in Eq. (5),

$$E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(3)} = \langle D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)} | \delta H | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle = \sum_{p \notin D} \delta H_{D_I; \alpha_I, p} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle. \quad (62)$$

The first equation is consistent with Eq. (17) in the non-degenerate case, which is expected since all degeneracy is already resolved at second order. We get to the second equation by noting that δH is diagonal in D . The last term here is yet to be determined.

In the case $\beta_I \neq \alpha_I$, the last term of Eq. (61) vanishes by state orthogonality, and we have

$$0 = \langle D_I; \beta_I^{(0)} | (E_{D_I}^{(1)} - \delta H) | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \langle D_I; \beta_I^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle. \quad (63)$$

Let us decompose the second order state correction in the above equation by

$$\begin{aligned} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)}\rangle = & \sum_{p \notin D} |\psi_p^{(0)}\rangle \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle + \sum_{J \neq I} \sum_{\alpha_J=1}^{N_J} |D_J; \alpha_J^{(0)}\rangle \langle D_J; \alpha_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle \\ & + \sum_{\gamma_I \neq \alpha_I} |D_I; \gamma_I^{(0)}\rangle \langle D_I; \gamma_I^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

This is similar to the treatment in Eq. (50), but with the “good basis”. The first component will survive in Eq. (63); the second component will not contribute due to state orthogonality and δH being diagonal in D ; the third component will not contribute by seeing $\delta H \rightarrow E_{D_I}^{(1)}$ in D_I . As a result, we have

$$0 = - \sum_{p \neq D} \delta H_{D_I; \beta_I, p} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \langle D_I; \beta_I^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle . \quad (65)$$

Combining with Eq. (60), we have

$$\begin{aligned} E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \langle D_I; \beta_I^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle &= \sum_{p \neq D} \delta H_{D_I; \beta_I, p} \frac{1}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} \left\{ E_{D_I}^{(1)} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle - \sum_{q \neq D} \delta H_{p, q} \langle \psi_q^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \sum_{J \neq I} \sum_{n_J=1}^{N_J} \delta H_{p, D_J; n_J} \langle D_J; n_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle - \sum_{\gamma_I \neq \alpha_I} \delta H_{p, D_I; \gamma_I} \langle D_I; \gamma_I^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle \right\} . \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

Note that in writing the last term, we have switched the summation to the “good basis”. Recall that we already know the first three terms on the right-hand side by Eqs. (49) and (53). Let us examine the last term,

$$- \sum_{p \neq D} \frac{\delta H_{D_I; \beta_I, p} \delta H_{p, D_I; \gamma_I}}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} = \langle D_I; \beta_I^{(0)} | \Delta_{D_I}^{(2)} | D_I; \gamma_I^{(0)} \rangle = E_{D_I; \beta_I}^{(2)} \delta_{\beta_I, \gamma_I} , \quad (67)$$

in which we recognize the $\Delta_{D_I}^{(2)}$ operator, as in Eq. (57), and recall that it is diagonal in the “good basis”. By assuming that the degeneracy is completely resolved at second order, i.e., $E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \neq E_{D_I; \beta_I}^{(2)}$ for $\alpha_I \neq \beta_I$, we can write Eq. (66) as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle D_I; \beta_I^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle &= \frac{1}{E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} - E_{D_I; \beta_I}^{(2)}} \sum_{p \neq D} \frac{\delta H_{D_I; \beta_I, p}}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} \left\{ - E_{D_I}^{(1)} \frac{\delta H_{p, D_I; \alpha_I}}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} + \sum_{q \neq D} \frac{\delta H_{p, q} \delta H_{q, D_I; \alpha_I}}{E_q^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \sum_{J \neq I} \sum_{n_J=1}^{N_J} \sum_{q \neq D} \frac{\delta H_{p, D_J; n_J} \delta H_{D_J; n_J, q} \delta H_{q, D_I; \alpha_I}}{(E_{D_I}^{(1)} - E_{D_J}^{(1)})(E_q^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)})} \right\} . \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

Up to this point, we complete the derivation of the first order state correction. One could write out the full expression by putting Eqs. (50), (49), (53), and (68) together. It is then straightforward to get the second order state correction that comes from outside D (i.e., \mathbb{V}_\perp) as in Eq. (60) and the third order energy correction as in Eq. (62).

We next project Eq. (48) onto $D - D_I$, using the “good basis” $\langle D_J; \beta_J^{(0)} |$ ($J \neq I$),

$$\begin{aligned} \langle D_J; \beta_J^{(0)} | (H_0 - E_D^{(0)}) | D_I; \alpha_I^{(3)} \rangle &= \langle D_J; \beta_J^{(0)} | (E_{D_I}^{(1)} - \delta H) | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle \\ &\quad + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \langle D_J; \beta_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(3)} \langle D_J; \beta_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)} \rangle . \end{aligned} \quad (69)$$

The terms on the left-hand side cancel out, and the last term on the right vanishes due to orthogonality.

$$0 = \langle D_J; \beta_J^{(0)} | (E_{D_I}^{(1)} - \delta H) | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \langle D_J; \beta_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle . \quad (70)$$

By the state decomposition as in Eq. (64), we obtain a second component of the second order state correction

$$\langle D_J; \alpha_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle = \frac{1}{E_{D_I}^{(1)} - E_{D_J}^{(1)}} \left\{ \sum_{p \neq D} \delta H_{D_J; \beta_J, p} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)} \rangle - E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \langle D_J; \beta_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)} \rangle \right\} . \quad (71)$$

Note that the terms on the right-hand side are known at this point.

Finally, we project Eq. (48) onto \mathbb{V}_\perp with $\langle \psi_p^{(0)} |$,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | (H_0 - E_D^{(0)}) |D_I; \alpha_I^{(3)}\rangle &= \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | (E_{D_I}^{(1)} - \delta H) |D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)}\rangle \\ &+ E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(3)} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)}\rangle . \end{aligned} \quad (72)$$

After some simplification, one gets

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(3)}\rangle &= \frac{1}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} \left\{ E_{D_I}^{(1)} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)}\rangle + E_{D_I}^{(2)} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(1)}\rangle - \sum_{q \neq D} \delta H_{p,q} \langle \psi_q^{(0)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)}\rangle \right. \\ &\left. - \sum_{J \neq I} \sum_{\beta_J=1}^{N_J} \delta H_{p,D_J; \beta_J} \langle D_J; \beta_J^{(0)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)}\rangle - \sum_{\gamma_I \neq \alpha_I} \delta H_{p,D_I; \gamma_I} \langle D_I; \gamma_I^{(0)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(2)}\rangle \right\} . \end{aligned} \quad (73)$$

They are two unknowns in this equation, the left-hand side, and the last term on the right-hand side. As we have exhausted the information of the eigenvalue equations up to $O(\lambda^3)$, to solve for the two unknowns, we need to go to the next order.

4. Higher order corrections

We can generalize the aforementioned procedure for higher order corrections, for which we will obtain a recursive relation of the corrections. Note that for states in the non-degenerate subspace, the formulas obtained in Sec. IA apply directly, and here we make the derivation for the states in the degenerate subspace D . The i -th order eigenstates in terms of the unperturbed basis states can be written as,

$$\begin{aligned} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(i)}\rangle &= (\mathbb{P}_{\mathbb{V}_\perp} + \mathbb{P}_{D-D_I} + \mathbb{P}_{D_I}) |D_I; \alpha_I^{(i)}\rangle \\ &= \sum_{p \in D} |\psi_p^{(0)}\rangle c_p^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i)} + \sum_{J \neq I} \sum_{\beta_J=1}^{N_J} |D_J; \beta_J^{(0)}\rangle c_{D_J; \beta_J}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i)} + \sum_{\gamma_I=1}^{N_I} |D_I; \gamma_I^{(0)}\rangle c_{D_I; \gamma_I}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i)} . \end{aligned} \quad (74)$$

in which $c_{\psi}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i)} \equiv \langle \psi |D_I; \alpha_I^{(i)}\rangle$. From the i -th order TISE, we can get $E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(i)}$, $c_p^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-1)}$, $c_{D_I; \beta_I}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-2)}$ ($\beta_I \neq \alpha_I$), $c_{D_J; \beta_J}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-1)}$ ($I \neq J$) in terms of lower order results, and a relation between $c_p^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i)}$ and $c_{D_I; \beta_I}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-1)}$ ($\beta_I \neq \alpha_I$) (which will be solved with the $(i+1)$ -th order equation). We have already shown this with the eigenvalue equations up to the third order. Let us proceed with the $i(\geq 3)$ -th order equation, as of Eq. (9),

$$H_0 |D_I; \alpha_I^{(i)}\rangle + \delta H |D_I; \alpha_I^{(i-1)}\rangle - \sum_{j=0}^i E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(j)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(i-j)}\rangle = 0 . \quad (75)$$

- Projection onto D_I

By projecting Eq. (75) onto a state in the D_I subspace, $\langle D_I; \gamma_I^{(0)} |$, we get

$$\langle D_I; \gamma_I^{(0)} | \delta H |D_I; \alpha_I^{(i-1)}\rangle - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(j)} \langle D_I; \gamma_I^{(0)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(i-j)}\rangle - E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(i)} \langle D_I; \gamma_I^{(0)} |D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)}\rangle = 0 . \quad (76)$$

In the case of $\gamma_I = \alpha_I$, we have

$$\boxed{E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(i)} = \langle D_I; \alpha_I^{(0)} | \delta H |D_I; \alpha_I^{(i-1)}\rangle} . \quad (77)$$

In the case of $\gamma_I \neq \alpha_I$, after expanding the state correction with Eq. (74), we get

$$\sum_{p \neq D} \delta H_{D_I; \gamma_I, p} c_p^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-1)} - E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} c_{D_I; \gamma_I}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-2)} - \sum_{j=3}^{i-1} E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(j)} c_{D_I; \gamma_I}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-j)} = 0. \quad (78)$$

The unknown terms at the current order are $c_p^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-1)}$ and $c_{D_I; \gamma_I}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-2)}$. We will solve it in combination with the $(i-1)$ -th order Eq. (80)

- Projection onto V_\perp
By projecting Eq. (75) onto V_\perp with $\langle \psi_p^{(0)} |$, we get

$$(E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}) \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(i)} \rangle + \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | \delta H | D_I; \alpha_I^{(i-1)} \rangle - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(j)} \langle \psi_p^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(i-j)} \rangle = 0, \quad (79)$$

Expanding the state correction with Eq. (74), we get

$$\boxed{c_p^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i)} = - \frac{1}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} \left[\sum_{q \neq D} \delta H_{p,q} c_q^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-1)} + \sum_{J \neq I} \sum_{\beta_J=1}^{N_J} \delta H_{p, D_J; \beta_J} c_{D_J; \beta_J}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-1)} + \sum_{\gamma_I=1}^{N_I} \delta H_{p, D_I; \gamma_I} c_{D_I; \gamma_I}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-1)} - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(j)} c_p^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-j)} \right].} \quad (80)$$

All terms except $c_p^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i)}$ and $c_{D_I; \beta_I}^{(D_I; \gamma_I)(i-1)}$ are known from lower order equations. These two terms will be solved together with Eq. (78) of the $(i+1)$ -th order TISE.

- Combination with the $(i-1)$ -th order equation

Plugging the $(i-1)$ -th order Eq. (80) into the first term of the i -th order Eq. (78), we obtain

$$\sum_{p \neq D} \frac{\delta H_{D_I; \gamma_I, p}}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} \left[\sum_{q \neq D} \delta H_{p,q} c_q^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-2)} + \sum_{J \neq I} \sum_{\beta_J=1}^{N_J} \delta H_{p, D_J; \beta_J} c_{D_J; \beta_J}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-2)} + \sum_{\rho_I=1}^{N_I} \delta H_{p, D_I; \rho_I} c_{D_I; \rho_I}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-2)} - \sum_{j=1}^{i-2} E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(j)} c_p^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-1-j)} \right] + E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)} c_{D_I; \gamma_I}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-2)} + \sum_{j=3}^{i-1} E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(j)} c_{D_I; \gamma_I}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-j)} = 0. \quad (81)$$

We simplify third term in the bracket by recognizing the $\Delta_{D_I}^{(2)}$ operator, as in Eq. (67), and obtain

$$\boxed{c_{D_I; \gamma_I}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-2)} = \frac{1}{E_{D_I; \gamma_I}^{(2)} - E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(2)}} \left\{ \sum_{p \neq D} \frac{\delta H_{D_I; \gamma_I, p}}{E_p^{(0)} - E_D^{(0)}} \left[\sum_{q \neq D} \delta H_{p,q} c_q^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-2)} + \sum_{J \neq I} \sum_{\beta_J=1}^{N_J} \delta H_{p, D_J; \beta_J} c_{D_J; \beta_J}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-2)} - \sum_{j=1}^{i-2} E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(j)} c_p^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-1-j)} \right] + \sum_{j=3}^{i-1} E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(j)} c_{D_I; \gamma_I}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-j)} \right\}.} \quad (82)$$

Back to the $(i-1)$ -th order Eq. (80), we obtain $c_p^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-1)}$.

- Projection onto $D_J (J \neq I)$

By projecting Eq. (75) onto a state in the D_J subspace, $\langle D_J; \beta_J^{(0)} |$, we get

$$\langle D_J; \beta_J^{(0)} | \delta H | D_I; \alpha_I^{(i-1)} \rangle - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(j)} \langle D_J; \beta_J^{(0)} | D_I; \alpha_I^{(i-j)} \rangle = 0, \quad (83)$$

Expanding the state correction with Eq. (74), we get

$$c_{D_J; \beta_J}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-1)} = \frac{1}{E_{D_I}^{(1)} - E_{D_J}^{(1)}} \left[\sum_{p \notin D} \delta H_{D_J; \beta_J, p} c_p^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-1)} - \sum_{j=2}^{i-1} E_{D_I; \alpha_I}^{(j)} c_{D_J; \beta_J}^{(D_I; \alpha_I)(i-j)} \right]. \quad (84)$$

Let us now summarize a general procedure for the perturbative theory of a degenerate system whose degeneracy is resolved at second order:

1. On a basis space generated by the unperturbed eigenstates of H_0 , identify the degenerate subspace D . Diagonalize δH in D , and take the δH eigenstates as the trial unperturbed states in the degenerate subspace.
2. Identify the remaining degeneracy in the trial basis space by writing $D = D_1 \oplus D_2 \oplus \dots$, such that different D_I s have different δH eigenvalues and each D_I subspace is degenerate in δH .
3. In each D_I subspace, construct the second-order perturbation matrix $\Delta_{D_I}^{(2)}$, according to Eq. (57). Then solve its secular equation, Eq. (58), by diagonalization and take the eigenstates as the correct unperturbed basis states.
4. Calculate the perturbation correction to the states whose unperturbed states are in the degenerate subspace D according to Eqs. (77), (80), (82), and (84).
5. Calculate the perturbation correction to the states whose unperturbed states are in the non-degenerate subspace according to Eqs. (17) and (21).

If degeneracy is not completely removed in the second order, one has to proceed to higher orders. It could also happen that the degeneracy is not broken in all orders, which we will encounter in the problem in Sec. II C. In such a scenario, one can exploit the symmetries of the Hamiltonian, if any, to decompose the problem Hilbert space into decoupled subspaces, so that the degeneracy is among but not within those subspaces. One can then apply the perturbation theory to each subspace separately.

II. APPLICATIONS

A. Toy model I

Let us consider a simple system whose degeneracy is partially lifted at first order and fully broken at second order. The full Hamiltonian is $H = H_0 + \lambda \delta H$ with λ being the coupling constant,

$$H_0 = \begin{bmatrix} a & & & \\ & b & & \\ & & b & \\ & & & b \end{bmatrix}, \quad \delta H = \begin{bmatrix} h & e_1 & e_2 & e_3 \\ e_1^* & c & 0 & 0 \\ e_2^* & 0 & c & 0 \\ e_3^* & 0 & 0 & d \end{bmatrix}. \quad (85)$$

We assume that $a \neq b$ and $c \neq d$. The unperturbed eigenstates and eigenvalues are,

$$\begin{aligned} E_1^{(0)} &= a, & |v_1^{(0)}\rangle &= [1, 0, 0, 0]^T, \\ E_2^{(0)} &= b, & |v_{2;1}^{(0)}\rangle &= [0, 1, 0, 0]^T, \\ & & |v_{2;2}^{(0)}\rangle &= [0, 0, 1, 0]^T, \\ & & |v_{2;3}^{(0)}\rangle &= [0, 0, 0, 1]^T. \end{aligned} \quad (86)$$

Here, one can recognize the degenerate subspace D that is spanned by $|v_{2;i}^{(0)}\rangle$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$), and its complementary subspace \mathbb{V}_\perp spanned by the basis state $|v_1^{(0)}\rangle$. Following the procedure developed in Secs. **IB** and **IC**, the next step is to diagonalize δH in D , which is readily done in this problem. The first order energy corrections are, according to Eqs.(17) and (25),

$$E_1^{(1)} = h, \quad E_2^{(1)} = c, \quad E_3^{(1)} = d. \quad (87)$$

We can see that the degeneracy is partially broken at first order, and the subspace can be decomposed into $D = D_1 \oplus D_2$, with D_1 spanned by $\{|v_{2;1}^{(0)}\rangle, |v_{2;2}^{(0)}\rangle\}$ and D_2 spanned by $|v_{2;3}^{(0)}\rangle$. This means that we need to diagonalize the second order energy fluctuation operator as defined in Eq. (57). For the subspace D_1 ,

$$\Delta_{D_1}^{(2)} = -\frac{1}{a-b} \begin{bmatrix} |e_1|^2 & e_1^* e_2 \\ e_1 e_2^* & |e_2|^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (88)$$

By solving the secular equation, Eq. (58), we obtain the ‘‘good’’ basis,

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_+^{(0)}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{|e_1|^2 + |e_2|^2}} \begin{bmatrix} 0, \frac{e_1^* e_2}{|e_2|}, |e_2|, 0 \end{bmatrix}^T, \\ |\psi_-^{(0)}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{|e_1|^2 + |e_2|^2}} \begin{bmatrix} 0, \frac{e_1^* e_2}{|e_1|}, -|e_1|, 0 \end{bmatrix}^T, \end{aligned} \quad (89)$$

and the second order state correction

$$E_+^{(2)} = -\frac{|e_1|^2 + |e_2|^2}{a-b}, \quad E_-^{(2)} = 0. \quad (90)$$

The subspace D_2 is one dimensional thus diagonal, so $|v_{2;3}^{(0)}\rangle$ is the ‘‘good’’ basis state, and its second order energy correction is

$$E_3^{(2)} = \Delta_{D_2}^{(2)} = -\frac{|e_3|^2}{a-b}. \quad (91)$$

Now, let us write out the Hamiltonian in the good basis $\{|v_1^{(0)}\rangle, |\psi_+^{(0)}\rangle, |v_{2;3}^{(0)}\rangle, |\psi_-^{(0)}\rangle\}$,

$$\bar{H}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} a & & & \\ & b & & \\ & & b & \\ \text{---} & & & b \end{pmatrix}, \quad \delta \bar{H} = \begin{pmatrix} h & \tilde{e}_1 & e_3 & \\ \tilde{e}_1^* & c & 0 & \\ e_3^* & 0 & d & \\ \text{---} & & & c \end{pmatrix}, \quad (92)$$

in which

$$\tilde{e}_1 = \langle v_1^{(0)} | \delta H | \psi_+^{(0)} \rangle = \frac{e_2}{|e_2|} \sqrt{|e_1|^2 + |e_2|^2}. \quad (93)$$

Since $\langle v_1^{(0)} | \delta H | \psi_-^{(0)} \rangle = 0$, the system decouples into two blocks, as shown in Eq. (92). The $|\psi_-^{(0)}\rangle$ state is the exact solution and the energy correction is complete at first order,

$$|\psi_-\rangle = |\psi_-^{(0)}\rangle, \quad E_-(\lambda) = b + \lambda c. \quad (94)$$

What remains to be solved is the top-left block. The corresponding subsystem contains degeneracy which is completely resolved at first order, so we can apply the procedure developed in Sec. IB. For the convenience of discussion, let us denote the basis states as

$$|\psi_1^{(0)}\rangle \equiv |v_1^{(0)}\rangle, \quad |\psi_{2;1}^{(0)}\rangle \equiv |\psi_+^{(0)}\rangle, \quad |\psi_{2;2}^{(0)}\rangle \equiv |v_{2;3}^{(0)}\rangle. \quad (95)$$

In the terminology used in Sec. IB, $\{|\psi_{2;1}^{(0)}\rangle, |\psi_{2;2}^{(0)}\rangle\}$ spans the degenerate subspace D , and $|\psi_1^{(0)}\rangle$ spans the non-degenerate subspace V_\perp . The results are, with states written in the basis of $\{|\psi_1^{(0)}\rangle, |\psi_{2;1}^{(0)}\rangle, |\psi_{2;2}^{(0)}\rangle\}$,

$$\begin{aligned} E_1(\lambda) &= a + \lambda h + \lambda^2 \frac{|\tilde{e}_1|^2 + |e_3|^2}{a-b} + \lambda^3 \frac{|\tilde{e}_1|^2(c-h) + |e_3|^2(d-h)}{(a-b)^2} + O(\lambda^4), \\ |\psi_1^{(1)}\rangle &= \left[0, \frac{\tilde{e}_1^*}{a-b}, \frac{e_3^*}{a-b} \right]^T \\ |\psi_1^{(2)}\rangle &= \left[0, \frac{\tilde{e}_1^*(c-h)}{(a-b)^2}, \frac{e_3^*(d-h)}{(a-b)^2} \right]^T. \end{aligned} \quad (96a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_{2;1}(\lambda) &= b + \lambda c - \lambda^2 \frac{|\tilde{e}_1|^2}{a-b} + \lambda^3 \frac{|\tilde{e}_1|^2}{(a-b)^2(c-d)} \left[(h-c)(c-d) + |e_3|^2 \right] + O(\lambda^4), \\ |\psi_{2;1}^{(1)}\rangle &= \left[-\frac{\tilde{e}_1}{a-b}, 0, \frac{e_3^* \tilde{e}_1}{(a-b)(c-d)} \right]^T \\ |\psi_{2;1}^{(2)}\rangle &= \left[\frac{\tilde{e}_1}{(a-b)^2(c-d)} \left[(h-c)(c-d) + |e_3|^2 \right], 0, \frac{\tilde{e}_1 e_3^*(h-c)}{(a-b)^2(c-d)} \right]^T. \end{aligned} \quad (96b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_{2;2}(\lambda) &= b + \lambda d - \lambda^2 \frac{|e_3|^2}{a-b} + \lambda^3 \frac{|e_3|^2}{(a-b)^2(d-c)} \left[(h-d)(d-c) + |\tilde{e}_1|^2 \right] + O(\lambda^4), \\ |\psi_{2;2}^{(1)}\rangle &= \left[-\frac{e_3}{a-b}, \frac{e_3 \tilde{e}_1^*}{(a-b)(d-c)}, 0 \right]^T \\ |\psi_{2;2}^{(2)}\rangle &= \left[\frac{e_3}{(a-b)^2(d-c)} \left[(h-d)(d-c) + |\tilde{e}_1|^2 \right], \frac{\tilde{e}_1^* e_3 (h-d)}{(a-b)^2(d-c)}, 0 \right]^T. \end{aligned} \quad (96c)$$

The results for $|\psi_{2;1}^{(0)}\rangle$ and $|\psi_{2;2}^{(0)}\rangle$ are symmetric by exchanging $c \leftrightarrow d$ and $\tilde{e}_1 \leftrightarrow e_3$. One can continue on with the developed formulas to find out higher order corrections.

B. Toy model II

We have seen that in the toy model I, after we found the ‘‘good basis’’ using the second order perturbation, the problem reduces to the case where degeneracy is resolved at first order. Here we consider a slightly more complicated system whose degeneracy is partially lifted at first order and fully broken at second order, and the system remains coupled after the second order perturbation. The problem Hamiltonian is

$$H_0 = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & & & & \\ & a_2 & & & \\ & & b & & \\ & & & b & \\ & & & & b \end{bmatrix}, \quad \delta H = \begin{bmatrix} h & 0 & m_1 & m_2 & m_3 \\ 0 & h & n_1 & n_2 & n_3 \\ m_1^* & n_1^* & c & 0 & 0 \\ m_2^* & n_2^* & 0 & c & 0 \\ m_3^* & n_3^* & 0 & 0 & d \end{bmatrix}. \quad (97)$$

We assume that $a_1 \neq a_2 \neq b$ and $c \neq d$. The unperturbed eigenstates and eigenvalues are,

$$\begin{aligned}
E_1^{(0)} &= a_1, & |v_1^{(0)}\rangle &= [1, 0, 0, 0, 0]^T, \\
E_2^{(0)} &= a_2, & |v_2^{(0)}\rangle &= [0, 1, 0, 0, 0]^T, \\
E_D^{(0)} &= b, & |v_{D;1}^{(0)}\rangle &= [0, 0, 1, 0, 0]^T, \\
& & |v_{D;2}^{(0)}\rangle &= [0, 0, 0, 1, 0]^T, \\
& & |v_{D;3}^{(0)}\rangle &= [0, 0, 0, 0, 1]^T.
\end{aligned} \tag{98}$$

Here, one can recognize the degenerate subspace D that is spanned by $|v_{D,i}^{(0)}\rangle$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$), and its complementary subspace \mathbb{V}_\perp spanned by the basis state $|v_1^{(0)}\rangle$ and $|v_2^{(0)}\rangle$. Following the procedure developed in Secs. **IB** and **IC**, the next step is to diagonalize δH in D , which is readily done. The first order energy corrections are, according to Eqs.(17) and (25),

$$E_1^{(1)} = E_2^{(1)} = h, \quad E_{D_1}^{(1)} = c, \quad E_{D_2}^{(1)} = d. \tag{99}$$

We can see that the degeneracy is partially broken at first order, and the subspace can be decomposed into $D = D_1 \oplus D_2$, with D_1 spanned by $\{|v_{D;1}^{(0)}\rangle, |v_{D;2}^{(0)}\rangle\}$ and D_2 spanned by $|v_{D;3}^{(0)}\rangle$. This means that we need to diagonalize the second order energy fluctuation operator as defined in Eq. (57). For the subspace D_1 ,

$$\Delta_{D_1}^{(2)} = - \begin{bmatrix} \frac{|m_1|^2}{a_1 - b} + \frac{|n_1|^2}{a_2 - b} & \frac{m_1^* m_2}{a_1 - b} + \frac{n_1^* n_2}{a_2 - b} \\ \frac{m_1 m_2^*}{a_1 - b} + \frac{n_1 n_2^*}{a_2 - b} & \frac{|m_2|^2}{a_1 - b} + \frac{|n_2|^2}{a_2 - b} \end{bmatrix} \equiv \begin{bmatrix} x & z \\ z^* & y \end{bmatrix}, \tag{100}$$

for which we defined x, y, z to compactify the expressions. The solution to its secular equation, Eq. (58), is

$$\epsilon_\pm = \frac{1}{2} \left[x + y \pm \sqrt{(x - y)^2 + 4|z|^2} \right], \quad |\psi_\pm\rangle = 1/\sqrt{|x - \epsilon_\mp|^2 + |z|^2} [x - \epsilon_\mp, z^*]^T. \tag{101}$$

Thereby we obtain the ‘‘good’’ basis states and their second order energy correction,

$$\begin{aligned}
|D_1; 1^{(0)}\rangle &\equiv |\psi_-\rangle, & E_{D_1;1}^{(2)} &= \epsilon_-, \\
|D_1; 2^{(0)}\rangle &\equiv |\psi_+\rangle, & E_{D_1;2}^{(2)} &= \epsilon_+.
\end{aligned} \tag{102}$$

The subspace D_2 is one dimensional thus diagonal, so $|D_2^{(0)}\rangle \equiv |v_{D;3}^{(0)}\rangle$ is the ‘‘good’’ basis state, and its second order energy correction is

$$E_{D_2}^{(2)} = \Delta_{D_2}^{(2)} = -\frac{|m_3|^2}{a_1 - b} - \frac{|n_3|^2}{a_2 - b}. \tag{103}$$

Now, let us write out the Hamiltonian in the good basis $\{|v_1^{(0)}\rangle, |v_2^{(0)}\rangle, |D_1; 1^{(0)}\rangle, |D_1; 2^{(0)}\rangle, |D_2^{(0)}\rangle\}$,

$$\tilde{H}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & & & & \\ & a_2 & & & \\ & & b & & \\ & & & b & \\ & & & & b \end{bmatrix}, \quad \delta\tilde{H} = \begin{bmatrix} h & 0 & \tilde{m}_1 & \tilde{m}_2 & m_3 \\ 0 & h & \tilde{n}_1 & \tilde{n}_2 & n_3 \\ \tilde{m}_1^* & \tilde{n}_1^* & c & 0 & 0 \\ \tilde{m}_2^* & \tilde{n}_2^* & 0 & c & 0 \\ m_3^* & n_3^* & 0 & 0 & d \end{bmatrix}, \tag{104}$$

in which

$$\tilde{m}_i = \langle v_1^{(0)} | \delta H | D_1; i^{(0)} \rangle, \quad \tilde{n}_i = \langle v_2^{(0)} | \delta H | D_1; i^{(0)} \rangle, \quad i = 1, 2. \quad (105)$$

The solution for the two states in the nondegenerate subspace \mathbb{V}_\perp can be obtained by following the nondegenerate perturbation theory, in specific Eqs. (17) and (21),

$$E_1(\lambda) = a_1 + \lambda h + \lambda^2 \frac{|\tilde{m}_1|^2 + |\tilde{m}_2|^2 + |m_3|^2}{a_1 - b} + O(\lambda^3), \quad (106a)$$

$$|v_1^{(1)}\rangle = \left[0, 0, \frac{\tilde{m}_1^*}{a_1 - b}, \frac{\tilde{m}_2^*}{a_1 - b}, \frac{m_3^*}{a_1 - b} \right]^T ;$$

$$E_2(\lambda) = a_2 + \lambda h + \lambda^2 \frac{|\tilde{n}_1|^2 + |\tilde{n}_2|^2 + |n_3|^2}{a_2 - b} + O(\lambda^3), \quad (106b)$$

$$|v_2^{(1)}\rangle = \left[0, 0, \frac{\tilde{n}_1^*}{a_2 - b}, \frac{\tilde{n}_2^*}{a_2 - b}, \frac{n_3^*}{a_2 - b} \right]^T .$$

The solution for the states in the degenerate subspaces D_1 and D_2 can be obtained by following the formulas derived in Sec. IC, in specific Eqs. (77), (80), (82), and (84). We have

$$E_{D_1;1}(\lambda) = b + \lambda c + \lambda^2 \left[-\frac{|\tilde{m}_1|^2}{a_1 - b} - \frac{|\tilde{n}_1|^2}{a_2 - b} \right] + O(\lambda^3),$$

$$|D_1; 1^{(1)}\rangle = -\frac{\tilde{m}_1}{a_1 - b} |v_1^{(0)}\rangle - \frac{\tilde{n}_1}{a_2 - b} |v_2^{(0)}\rangle$$

$$+ \frac{1}{\epsilon_+ - \epsilon_-} \left\{ \frac{\tilde{m}_2^*}{a_1 - b} \left[-\frac{\tilde{m}_1(h-c)}{a_1 - b} + \frac{m_3}{c-d} \left(-\frac{m_3^* \tilde{m}_1}{a_1 - b} - \frac{n_3^* \tilde{n}_1}{a_2 - b} \right) \right] \right.$$

$$+ \left. \frac{\tilde{n}_2^*}{a_2 - b} \left[-\frac{\tilde{n}_1(h-c)}{a_2 - b} + \frac{n_3}{c-d} \left(-\frac{m_3^* \tilde{m}_1}{a_1 - b} - \frac{n_3^* \tilde{n}_1}{a_2 - b} \right) \right] \right\} |D_1; 2^{(0)}\rangle$$

$$+ \frac{1}{c-d} \left(-\frac{m_3^* \tilde{m}_1}{a_1 - b} - \frac{n_3^* \tilde{n}_1}{a_2 - b} \right) |D_2^{(0)}\rangle ; \quad (107a)$$

$$E_{D_1;2}(\lambda) = b + \lambda c + \lambda^2 \left[-\frac{|\tilde{m}_2|^2}{a_1 - b} - \frac{|\tilde{n}_2|^2}{a_2 - b} \right] + O(\lambda^3),$$

$$|D_1; 2^{(1)}\rangle = -\frac{\tilde{m}_2}{a_1 - b} |v_1^{(0)}\rangle - \frac{\tilde{n}_2}{a_2 - b} |v_2^{(0)}\rangle$$

$$+ \frac{1}{\epsilon_+ - \epsilon_-} \left\{ \frac{\tilde{m}_1^*}{a_1 - b} \left[-\frac{\tilde{m}_2(h-c)}{a_1 - b} + \frac{m_3}{c-d} \left(-\frac{m_3^* \tilde{m}_2}{a_1 - b} - \frac{n_3^* \tilde{n}_2}{a_2 - b} \right) \right] \right.$$

$$+ \left. \frac{\tilde{n}_1^*}{a_2 - b} \left[-\frac{\tilde{n}_2(h-c)}{a_2 - b} + \frac{n_3}{c-d} \left(-\frac{m_3^* \tilde{m}_2}{a_1 - b} - \frac{n_3^* \tilde{n}_2}{a_2 - b} \right) \right] \right\} |D_1; 1^{(0)}\rangle$$

$$+ \frac{1}{c-d} \left(-\frac{m_3^* \tilde{m}_2}{a_1 - b} - \frac{n_3^* \tilde{n}_2}{a_2 - b} \right) |D_2^{(0)}\rangle , \quad (107b)$$

and

$$E_{D_2}(\lambda) = b + \lambda d + \lambda^2 \left[-\frac{|m_3|^2}{a_1 - b} - \frac{|n_3|^2}{a_2 - b} \right] + O(\lambda^3),$$

$$|D_2^{(1)}\rangle = -\frac{m_3}{a_1 - b} |v_1^{(0)}\rangle - \frac{n_3}{a_2 - b} |v_2^{(0)}\rangle + \frac{1}{d-c} \left(-\frac{m_3 \tilde{m}_1^*}{a_1 - b} - \frac{n_3 \tilde{n}_1^*}{a_2 - b} \right) |D_1; 1^{(0)}\rangle$$

$$+ \frac{1}{d-c} \left(-\frac{m_3 \tilde{m}_2^*}{a_1 - b} - \frac{n_3 \tilde{n}_2^*}{a_2 - b} \right) |D_1; 2^{(0)}\rangle . \quad (108)$$

C. Dressed quark prototype

We now turn to the dressed quark for an instructive application of the time-independent perturbation theory. In the Hamiltonian formalism of Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD), a dressed quark is described by the eigenstate of the QCD Hamiltonian in the expanded Fock space $|q\rangle + |qg\rangle + \dots$

Let us consider a simplified Hilbert space of $|q\rangle + |qg\rangle$, in which the $|q\rangle$ sector contains the two spin projection states of the quark, namely $s_q = \pm 1/2$, and the $|qg\rangle$ sector contains the four quark-gluon spin states, namely $\{s_q, s_g\} = \{+1/2, +1\}, \{+1/2, -1\}, \{-1/2, +1\}$, and $\{-1/2, -1\}$. All other quantum numbers of those basis states, including color and momentum (total for quark-gluon states), are chosen to be the same, such that the quark and the quark-gluon states can couple to each other through the $q \leftrightarrow qg$ vertex interaction. The resulting Hamiltonian of the problem therefore has the following structure as $H = H_0 + \lambda \delta H$,

$$H_0 = \begin{bmatrix} a & & & & & \\ & a & & & & \\ & & b & & & \\ & & & b & & \\ & & & & b & \\ & & & & & b \end{bmatrix}, \quad \delta H = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & u^R & v^R & w & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -w & v^L & u^L \\ u^L & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ v^L & -w & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ w & v^R & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & u^R & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (109)$$

The unperturbed Hamiltonian H_0 is degenerate in the $|q\rangle$ and the $|qg\rangle$ sectors, with $a, b > 0$, denoting the kinetic energy of the quark and the quark-gluon states respectively. The perturbation δH is the interaction for the gluon emission and absorption, and its structure extracted from the quark-gluon vertex interaction, in which $u^{R/L} = ue^{\pm i\theta_u}$, $v^{R/L} = ve^{\pm i\theta_v}$, and $u, v, w > 0$.

The unperturbed eigenstates and eigenvalues are,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{1,i}^{(0)} &= a, \quad (i = 1, 2), & |v_{1,1}^{(0)}\rangle &= [1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]^T, \\ & & |v_{1,2}^{(0)}\rangle &= [0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0]^T, \\ E_{2,j}^{(0)} &= b, \quad (j = 1, 2, 3, 4), & |v_{2,1}^{(0)}\rangle &= [0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0]^T, \\ & & |v_{2,2}^{(0)}\rangle &= [0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0]^T, \\ & & |v_{2,3}^{(0)}\rangle &= [0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0]^T, \\ & & |v_{2,4}^{(0)}\rangle &= [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1]^T. \end{aligned} \quad (110)$$

There are two degenerate subspaces, \mathbb{V}_1 spanned by $v_{1,i}^{(0)}$, and \mathbb{V}_2 spanned by $v_{2,j}^{(0)}$. To carry out the degenerate perturbative calculation, we first need to find a basis space such that δH is diagonal in each degenerate subspace of H_0 . This is already true, since the perturbation is zero within each subspace, which also implies that the degeneracy is not broken at first order, and we need to treat the degeneracy at second order.

Let us find the second order energy fluctuation operator as defined in Eq. (57). For the subspace \mathbb{V}_1 ,

$$\Delta_{\mathbb{V}_1}^{(2)} = -\frac{1}{b-a} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \Delta^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (111)$$

where we define $\Delta^2 \equiv u^2 + v^2 + w^2$. It is already diagonal, which means that the original basis is the already the good basis in \mathbb{V}_1 , and the diagonal elements are the second order energy correction,

$$E_{1,1}^{(2)} = E_{1,2}^{(2)} = -\frac{1}{b-a} \Delta^2, \quad \{|\psi_{1,1}^{(0)}\rangle, |\psi_{1,2}^{(0)}\rangle\} = \{|v_{1,1}^{(0)}\rangle, |v_{1,2}^{(0)}\rangle\}. \quad (112)$$

For the subspace \mathbb{V}_2 ,

$$\Delta_{\mathbb{V}_2}^{(2)} = \frac{1}{b-a} \begin{bmatrix} u^2 & u^L v^R & u^L w & 0 \\ u^R v^L & v^2 + w^2 & 0 & -u^L w \\ u^R w & 0 & v^2 + w^2 & u^L v^R \\ 0 & -u^R w & u^R v^L & u^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (113)$$

By diagonalizing $\Delta_{\mathbb{V}_2}^{(2)}$, we find the good basis and the second-order energy correction simultaneously,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{2,1}^{(2)} &= 0, & |\psi_{2,1}^{(0)}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\Delta u} [0, 0, -u^L v^R, u^2, 0, w u^R]^T, \\ E_{2,2}^{(2)} &= 0, & |\psi_{2,2}^{(0)}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\Delta u} [0, 0, -w u^L, 0, u^2, -v^L u^R]^T, \\ E_{2,3}^{(2)} &= \frac{\Delta^2}{b-a}, & |\psi_{2,3}^{(0)}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\Delta} [0, 0, u^L, v^L, w, 0]^T, \\ E_{2,4}^{(2)} &= \frac{\Delta^2}{b-a}, & |\psi_{2,4}^{(0)}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\Delta} [0, 0, 0, -w, v^R, u^R]^T. \end{aligned} \quad (114)$$

Note that the degeneracy is not completely broken at second order. Let us write out the Hamiltonian in the good basis $\{|\psi_{n,i}^{(0)}\rangle\}$,

$$\bar{H}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} a & & & & & \\ & a & & & & \\ & & b & & & \\ & & & b & & \\ & & & & b & \\ & & & & & b \end{bmatrix}, \quad \delta\bar{H} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \Delta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \Delta \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \Delta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \Delta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (115)$$

The system decouple into three blocks as $\bar{H}_0 = \bar{H}_{0,1} \oplus \bar{H}_{0,2} \oplus \bar{H}_{0,3}$ and $\delta\bar{H} = \delta\bar{H}_1 \oplus \delta\bar{H}_2 \oplus \delta\bar{H}_3$, with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{V}_{Q,1} &= \{|\psi_{1,1}^{(0)}\rangle, |\psi_{2,3}^{(0)}\rangle\}, & \bar{H}_{0,1} &= \begin{bmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & b \end{bmatrix}, & \delta\bar{H}_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \Delta \\ \Delta & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbb{V}_{Q,2} &= \{|\psi_{1,2}^{(0)}\rangle, |\psi_{2,4}^{(0)}\rangle\}, & \bar{H}_{0,2} &= \begin{bmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & b \end{bmatrix}, & \delta\bar{H}_2 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \Delta \\ \Delta & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbb{V}_{qse} &= \{|\psi_{2,1}^{(0)}\rangle, |\psi_{2,2}^{(0)}\rangle\}, & \bar{H}_{0,3} &= \begin{bmatrix} b & 0 \\ 0 & b \end{bmatrix}, & \delta\bar{H}_3 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (116)$$

We can then proceed the perturbation calculation for each block separately. The structure of the two subspace $\mathbb{V}_{Q,1}$ and $\mathbb{V}_{Q,2}$ are identical. Physically, this corresponds to that the spin-up and the spin-down dressed quarks are degenerate. Using the nondegenerate perturbation theory, in specific Eqs. (17) and (21), we get the solution for each subspace. For $\mathbb{V}_{Q,1}$,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{1,1}(\lambda) &= a + \lambda^2 \frac{\Delta^2}{a-b} + \lambda^4 \frac{\Delta^4}{(b-a)^3} - \lambda^5 \frac{2\Delta^6}{(b-a)^5} + O(\lambda^8), \\ |\psi_{1,1}(\lambda)\rangle &= |\psi_{1,1}^{(0)}\rangle - \lambda \frac{\Delta}{b-a} |\psi_{2,3}^{(0)}\rangle + \lambda^3 \frac{\Delta^3}{(b-a)^3} |\psi_{2,3}^{(0)}\rangle - \lambda^5 \frac{2\Delta^5}{(b-a)^5} |\psi_{2,3}^{(0)}\rangle + O(\lambda^7), \\ E_{2,3}(\lambda) &= b + \lambda^2 \frac{\Delta^2}{b-a} + \lambda^4 \frac{\Delta^4}{(a-b)^3} - \lambda^5 \frac{2\Delta^6}{(a-b)^5} + O(\lambda^8), \\ |\psi_{2,3}(\lambda)\rangle &= |\psi_{2,3}^{(0)}\rangle - \lambda \frac{\Delta}{a-b} |\psi_{1,1}^{(0)}\rangle + \lambda^3 \frac{\Delta^3}{(a-b)^3} |\psi_{1,1}^{(0)}\rangle - \lambda^5 \frac{2\Delta^5}{(a-b)^5} |\psi_{1,1}^{(0)}\rangle + O(\lambda^7). \end{aligned} \quad (117)$$

The result is the same for $\mathbb{V}_{Q,2}$ if we swap indices “1,1”→“1,2” and “2,3”→“2,4”. The subspace \mathbb{V}_{qge} is perturbation-free, so the unperturbed eigenstates are the exact solution,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{2,1}(\lambda) &= b, & |\psi_{2,1}(\lambda)\rangle &= |\psi_{2,1}^{(0)}\rangle, \\ E_{2,2}(\lambda) &= b, & |\psi_{2,2}(\lambda)\rangle &= |\psi_{2,2}^{(0)}\rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (118)$$

Now let us find the exact solutions of the full Hamiltonian H by diagonalization. The eigenvector space is degenerate into three subspaces, and the eigenvalues and eigenstates are,

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= \frac{1}{2}(a + b - \eta), & |\phi_{1,1}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{(a-b-\eta)^2 + 4\lambda^2\Delta^2}} [b - a + \eta, 0, -2\lambda u^L, -2\lambda v^L, -2\lambda w, 0]^T, \\ & & |\phi_{1,2}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{(a-b-\eta)^2 + 4\lambda^2\Delta^2}} [0, b - a + \eta, 0, 2\lambda w, -2\lambda v^R, -2\lambda u^R]^T, \\ E_2 &= \frac{1}{2}(a + b + \eta), & |\phi_{2,1}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{(a-b+\eta)^2 + 4\lambda^2\Delta^2}} [a - b + \eta, 0, 2\lambda u^L, 2\lambda v^L, 2\lambda w, 0]^T, \\ & & |\phi_{2,2}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{(a-b+\eta)^2 + 4\lambda^2\Delta^2}} [0, a - b + \eta, 0, -2\lambda w, 2\lambda v^R, 2\lambda u^R]^T, \\ E_3 &= b, & |\phi_{3,1}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\Delta u} [0, 0, -u^L v^R, u^2, 0, w u^R]^T, \\ & & |\phi_{3,2}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\Delta u} [0, 0, -w u^L, 0, u^2, -v^L u^R]^T. \end{aligned} \quad (119)$$

Here, we define $\eta \equiv \sqrt{(a-b)^2 + 4\lambda^2\Delta^2}$ to reduce the clutter in the algebra. In comparison with the perturbative results we obtained: $\phi_{1,1}$ and $\phi_{1,2}$ are $\psi_{1,1}$ and $\psi_{1,2}$ upon normalization, $\phi_{2,1}$ and $\phi_{2,2}$ are $\psi_{2,3}$ and $\psi_{2,4}$ upon normalization, and $\phi_{3,1}$ and $\phi_{3,2}$ are just $\psi_{2,1}$ and $\psi_{2,2}$. The eigenvalues also agree, seeing that $E_1 = E_{1,1} = E_{1,2}$, $E_2 = E_{2,3} = E_{2,4}$ and $E_3 = E_{2,1} = E_{2,2}$.

In this problem, the full Hamiltonian is degenerate, and the degeneracy is not broken through perturbation at any order. Such degeneracy has an associated symmetry operator, say \mathbf{S} , which H commutes with. Then the Hamiltonian is block-diagonal in the \mathbf{S} eigenspace such that the states in each block have the same \mathbf{S} eigenvalue. One can then solve each block separately, without dealing with the degeneracy associated with \mathbf{S} . Here, the \mathbf{S} operator is essentially the quark spin projection operator (containing the relative orbital angular momentum between the quark and the gluon), and we are able to block diagonalize the Hamiltonian (i.e., reordering \bar{H}) upon diagonalizing $\Delta^{(2)}$ according to the procedure developed for the degenerate perturbation theory when degeneracy is lifted at second order.

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Appendix A: An alternative treatment using projectors

In this appendix, we provide an alternative treatment of the degenerate perturbation theory when degeneracy is completely resolved at first order, as described in sec. **IB**. We follow the method developed in Chapter 5 of Ref. [2], using projectors.

Let P_0 be a projection operator onto D and $P_1 = I - P_0$ the complementary operator on to V_\perp , explicitly

$$P_0 = \sum_{n=1}^g |D; n^{(0)}\rangle \langle D; n^{(0)}|, \quad P_1 = \sum_{p \notin D} |\psi_p^{(0)}\rangle \langle \psi_p^{(0)}|. \quad (\text{A1})$$

We separate the eigenvalue equation, Eq. (3), into two equations by projecting with P_0 and P_1 ,

$$(E_{D;n} - E_D^{(0)} - \lambda P_0 \delta H) P_0 |D; n\rangle - \lambda P_0 \delta H P_1 |D; n\rangle = 0, \quad (\text{A2a})$$

$$(E_{D;n} - H_0 - \lambda P_1 \delta H P_1) P_1 |D; n\rangle - \lambda P_1 \delta H P_0 |D; n\rangle = 0. \quad (\text{A2b})$$

We invert Eq. (A2b), noting that $E_{D;n} \neq E_p$ where $p \notin D$, and get

$$P_1 |D; n\rangle = P_1 \frac{\lambda}{E_{D;n} - H_0 - \lambda \delta H} P_1 \delta H P_0 |D; n\rangle. \quad (\text{A3})$$

At first order, we have

$$P_1 |D; n^{(1)}\rangle = \sum_{p \notin D} \frac{|\psi_p^{(0)}\rangle \delta H_{p,D_n}}{E_D^{(0)} - E_p^{(0)}}, \quad (\text{A4})$$

which is equivalent to Eq. (27).

We substitute Eq. (A3) into Eq. (A2a) and obtain

$$0 = \left(E_{D;n} - E_D^{(0)} - \lambda P_0 \delta H P_0 - \lambda^2 P_0 \delta H P_1 \frac{1}{E_{D;n} - H_0 - \lambda \delta H} P_1 \delta H P_0 \right) P_0 |D; n\rangle. \quad (\text{A5})$$

We will now expand the above equation in series of λ with Eqs. (22) and (23).² At first order in λ , we have

$$0 = (E_{D;n}^{(1)} - P_0 \delta H P_0) P_0 |D; n^{(0)}\rangle, \quad (\text{A6})$$

which is equivalent to Eq. (25).

To obtain higher order corrections to the energy we can project Eq. (A2a) onto $\langle D; n^{(0)}|$, applying the normalization constraint $\langle n^0 | n \rangle = 1$, we get

$$E_{D;n} = E_D^{(0)} + \lambda \langle D; n^{(0)} | \delta H | D; n \rangle. \quad (\text{A7})$$

The i -the order energy correction thus follows as

$$E_{D;n}^{(i)} = \langle D; n^{(0)} | \delta H | D; n^{(i-1)} \rangle. \quad (\text{A8})$$

This formula is the same as Eq. (17) in non-degenerate perturbation theory but using the new states.

Equation (A5) at second order becomes

$$0 = \left(E_{D;n}^{(1)} - P_0 \delta H P_0 \right) |D; n^{(1)}\rangle + \left[E_{D;n}^{(2)} - P_0 \delta H P_1 \frac{1}{E_D^{(0)} - H_0} P_1 \delta H P_0 \right] P_0 |D; n^{(0)}\rangle. \quad (\text{A9})$$

² One can apply the Taylor series $\frac{1}{a-\lambda x} = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{\lambda x}{a^2} + \frac{\lambda^2 x^2}{a^3} + \mathcal{O}(\lambda^3)$.

By projecting it onto $\langle D; n^{(0)}|$, we get Eq. (32). By projecting it onto $\langle D; k^{(0)}|$ where $k \neq n$, and assuming that the degeneracy is completely resolved at first order, we recover Eq. (31).

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